

Review Article

Technical Vocational Education and Training (TVET) as A Panacea to Solving Nigeria's Youths' Problem of Unemployment

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Abstract

This paper examines the potency Technical Vocational Education and Training (TVET) as a Panacea to Solving Nigeria's Youths' Problem of Unemployment. Nigeria, an emerging economy with an estimated population of about 200 million is battling with poverty and unemployment problems consequently the country's quest for technological progress, industrialization and economic development is 'snail – speeding' and very unimpressive. TVET has been recognized worldwide as a tool for empowering people, especially the youth, for sustainable livelihood and social-economic development. This paper adopted a conceptual approach to explore how Technical Vocational Education and Training as a Panacea to Solving Nigeria's Youths' Problem of Unemployment. Materials were generated via internet, textbooks and other documents relevant to the study. The Nigerian government had initiated several youth empowerment programmes through TVET, but a lot of these programmes lack structure and their impact not felt by the nation's youths. This is evident in the substantial number of youth that still lack work skills-which often results to unemployment, insecurity, loss of lives and properties and chaos. The findings based on the literature reviewed showed TVET is backed up with the availability of materials, infrastructure, hard and soft skills coupled with good will on the part of government could be the vitally needed solution to the problem of graduates' employability in Nigeria. Truly, the battle against youth unemployment cannot be won without tertiary institutions collaborating with the private sector of the economy. This forms the thrust of this paper. It was recommended among others that educational institutions offering technical education programmes should tap the dynamisms and synergies of the 21st century workplace to the full to produce technical education graduates who can fit in and succeed in the 21st century world of work.

Keywords: *Employability, Unemployment, Employment Creation, Technical Vocational Education, Training, Economic Progress.*

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Introduction

“We are witnessing a young generation frustrated by the chronic mismatch between skills and work. The best answer to the economic downturn and youth unemployment is to ensure that young people acquire the basic skills and relevant training they need to enter the world of work with confidence. Irina Bokova, UNESCO’s Director-General, 2000”

The cyberspace is currently facing a youth employment crisis despite sizeable gains in educational access and attainment across the world over the past decade, young people aged 15-24 are now three times more likely than adults to be unemployed (ILO, 2012).

A growing mismatch between the supply and demand for skills, which disproportionately affects young people in developing countries, is one of the main reasons for high youth unemployment across the world. There is an unprecedented oversupply of social science and business graduates but a low number of graduates able to fill high vacancies in agri-business or engineering across sub-Saharan Africa, (African Economic Outlook, 2012).

The World Bank (2012) links high youth unemployment in sub-Sahara Africa particularly to poorly conceptualized, inadequate, and ill-delivered technical and vocational education and training. The United States is not the only society that appreciates skills acquired through vocational and technical education, Nigeria can therefore not be an exception if we are to tackle head on the ravaging unemployment problem which has become a major problem bedeviling the lives of Nigerian youth, causing increased militancy, violent crimes, kidnappings, restiveness and socially delinquent behavior.

In many countries, young people lack basic foundational skills and therefore have difficulties finding decent jobs or becoming self-employed. These issues often affect rural youth and young women more than other groups (ILO, 2012). In 23 sub-Saharan African countries, at least half of young people aged 15-19 lack basic literacy and numeracy skills because they never attended school or dropped out early (UNESCO, 2012: 179). In Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development, OECD countries, unemployment among young people who have not completed secondary school is nearly twice as high as among those with tertiary degrees.

It is generally agreed that the progress of a country and the development of its manpower is the primary aim of education. Through education, people are able to develop their knowledge and skills in order to be able to survive. This implies that any nation including Nigeria cannot progress as expected without a good and effective education that is planned to provide the necessary competencies and skills to its citizens for national development. In this sense, national development can be seen as the attainment of economic growth leading to economic competitiveness, high standard of living and self-reliance.

Technical and Vocational Education and Training (TVET) is an aspect of education that has long been introduced into the mainstream of Nigeria education system. Its frequent usage by a number of countries around the world, including the International Labour Organization (ILO) and the United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization (UNESCO) is synonymous with the term Vocational and Technical Education (VTE) as used in the education policy document of Nigeria. Consequently, the definition of VTE is similar to the definition of TVET as used in a joint publication by the UNESCO and ILO (2002) which refers to ‘... those aspects of educational process involving, in addition to general education, the study of technologies and related sciences, and the acquisition of practical skills, attitudes, understanding and knowledge relating to occupations in various sectors of economic and social life.’ The UNESCO (2005) stated that the aspect that differentiates TVET from other forms of education and training are its emphasis on work productivity. No wonder, Awotunde (2000) viewed TVE T as an integral part of national development strategies in many societies, because of the impact on human resource development and work productivity. From these stand-points, TVET worldwide aims at training and mobilizing competent and skilled workforce for technological progress, industrialization and national development, because of its emphasis on work productivity.

The United Nations Educational Scientific and Cultural Organization (UNESCO) and the International Labour Organization (ILO) recommendations of 2000 on technical and vocational education and training for the twenty-first century, defined TVET as those aspects of the educational process involving in addition to general education, the study of technologies and related sciences and the acquisition of practical skills, attitudes, understanding and knowledge relating to occupations in various sectors of economic and social life.

Technical and vocational education and training (TVET) is increasingly being viewed as a potential solution to the youth employment crisis. TVET's orientation towards the world of work and the acquisition of employable skills means that it is well placed to overcome the skills mismatch issues that have impeded smooth education-to-employment transitions for many young people.

It refers to deliberate interventions to bring about learning which would make people more productive (or simply adequately productive) in designated areas of economic activity (e.g., economic sectors, occupations, specific work tasks).

TVET thus equips people not only with vocational and technical skills, but with a broad range of knowledge, skills and attitudes that are now recognized as indispensable for meaningful participation in work and life. It entails the enrichment of the capabilities that influence the effective psychomotor or cognitive domains of individual in readiness for entry into the world of work in order to satisfy their intrinsic and extrinsic needs, values, work and aspirations such that local and national needs would be met.

Its relevant practical training component is widely recognized as the key to any nation becoming technologically relevant and internationally competitive in the world market. TVET is also regarded as the most effective means of empowering the citizenry to stimulate sustainable national development, enhance employment, improve the quality of life, reduce poverty, limit the incidence of social vices due to joblessness and promote a culture of peace, freedom and democracy (FME, 2000). It is not gainsaying that developed nations such as Japan, China, USA and Germany have attained tremendous height in terms of industrialization as a result of consistent investment in technical vocational education and training of its citizen. In many of these countries, high schools offer TVET for lifelong trade for Youth's empowerment (Ibeneme, 2011). Thus, TVET has been an integral part of national development strategies in many societies because of its impact on productivity and economic development.

The high rate of unemployment in the country has been alerted further by some statistical reports. For instance, the number of unemployed youths despite numerous TVET courses offered at the tertiary level is put at 68 million (Ministry of Youth Development, 2012). The NBS (2011) points out that 50% of Nigerians between the ages of 15 and 24 and living in urban areas were unemployed in 2009, about 17.3% of those in the age group of 25 to 44 were unemployed in the same year, while 10% of Nigerians in the age group of 45 to 59 and living in urban areas were unemployed in the same year. A careful look at this

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report reveals that unemployment rates are higher among young youths. Furthermore, the national unemployment rate which was 13.1% in 2000, moved to about 15% in 2008, jumped to 20% in 2009, moved to about 21.1% in 2010, and moved to 23.9% in 2011. Based on this trend, higher rates are projected for the coming years.

Causes of Youth Unemployment

Some of the causes of youth unemployment include: Lack of relevant skills, Lack of information about the labour market: Lack of work experience: Lack of entrepreneurship skills to create new jobs and Inhospitable investment climate discouraging entrepreneurship and job creation:

The purpose of this paper is to give credence to the importance of the collaboration between the gown and the town in the promotion in Nigeria in order to alleviate the sufferings of the youth populace occasioned by unemployment as a result of skills mismatch at the detriment of the society.

Youth Empowerment and Sustainable Development

Though TVET can be a decisive instrument for youth to participate in the work force and to improve their living conditions and social status, yet the current preoccupation with the university education in Nigeria reduces economic opportunities of those who are more oriented towards work than academe, not everyone needs a university education, but who would employ them if everyone became a university graduate?

Graduates of vocational and technical institutions are the empowered youths, they are highly skilled entrepreneurs, many of the so called "expatriate engineers" who are being paid huge sum of money in dollars to build roads and bridges in Nigeria are graduates of vocational colleges, yet Nigeria is not taking this sector seriously.

Youth empowerment by TVET education is therefore a sure means to aid sustainable development if utmost consideration is given to the sector.

Integrating Skill Development in Education for All (EFA) Ensuring that all learning needs of young people and adults are met through equitable access to appropriate learning and life skills programmes is one of the six education for all (EFA) goals established at the world education forum in Dakar 2000. So the provision of vocational skills training youth empowerment should therefore constitute an important component in national strategies if the EFA goal is to be achieved.

Incorporating TVET in the EFA programme is a necessity in all developing countries because it advocates for flexible access to learning and training throughout life while downplaying the shortcoming of the beneficiary in order to accommodate a larger group for sustainable development and improve/enhance productivity.

Vocational Technical Education to the Rescue

Technology education was formerly limited. Technical and vocational education is a form of education designed to equip the learners for gainful employment. It is that part of education that provides the skills, knowledge and attitude necessary for effective employment in specific occupation. Technical and vocational educations are the most reliable vehicles for self-sustenance, economic prosperity and political supremacy of a nation over others.

It is also a form of education that includes preparation for employment in any industry for specialized education for which there is societal needs and which can most appropriately be acquired in schools. According to the Federal Government of Nigeria (2004), technical and vocational education is a comprehensive term referring to those aspects of the educational process involving in addition to general education, the study of technologies and related sciences and the acquisition of practical skills, attitudes, understandings, and knowledge relating to occupations in various sectors of economic life.

Technical and vocational education is particularly relevant in solving the present economic problems in the country due to the advancement in technology, occupational mobility, high rate of unemployment and increasing number of women in workforce. It is concerned with producing the manpower who will apply scientific skill towards the improvement and solution of the environmental problems, thus making the environment more conducive and useful for mankind.

The adoption of technical and vocational education in any country is for the following: Skill and knowledge required in the society, Economic development, For work and economic activity, For job creation and Self-respect, social contact and participation. From the foregoing, technical and TVE education is a skill development programme which is highly required for the country's quest to be one of the 20st economic nations of the world by the year 2020.

The Goals of Technical and Vocational Education

The goals of technical and vocational education according to the Federal Republic of Nigeria (2013) is to: Provide trained manpower in the applied sciences, technology and business particularly at craft, advanced craft and technical levels, Provide the technical knowledge and vocational skills necessary for agricultural, commercial and economic development and Give training and impart the necessary skills to individual who shall be self-reliant economically.

Though the goals of technical and vocational education as stated above are quite laudable but the implementation of the programme has fallen short of expectation. The slow pace of unemployment, the increasing rate of unemployment and the inability of the country to provide the good things of life to her citizens are evidences in this direction.

The Benefits of Technical and Vocational Education to the Youths

There is a need to establish a secure and poverty free nation for youth to become influential members of any society. Poverty, hunger, homelessness society, sickness and lack of security are paramount issues that require immediate attention of the Nigerian government, if young people are expected to become leaders of the future.

For many youths in Nigeria, these problems are daily challenges, when they cannot feed, clothe or shelter themselves or their immediate family, they surely cannot realize their full potentials, since the need for survival is so overwhelming a good number of young people have fallen victim to the pressures of survival and have ended up as arm robbers, prostitutes scammers, or militants fighting whatever cause, give them a glimmer of hope The problems enumerated above can only be solved only if Technical and vocational education is factored into relevance in any country that is desirous of creating uncommon prosperity for the populace.

Technical and vocational education and training plays an essential role in improving the wellbeing of youths and communities. It increases productivity, empowers individual to become self-reliant and stimulates entrepreneurship. Businesses are more willing to invest in a community with strong human resources (Chinwe, 2008). Skills development can therefore contribute to strengthening the social links of a community by promoting employment creativity and sustainable means of subsistence. Vocational education and job training programme has been an integral part of national developments strategies in many societies because of the impact on human resources development, productivity, and economic growth. Despite it's proven contribution Nigeria does not seem to give

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vocational education the attention it deserves; and that appears one of the reasons for the rising unemployment and poverty in the society. Vocational education is therefore the missing link in Nigeria's development policy.

Although TVET seems deficient in 'citizenship or leadership training' (Friedman, 1982), they could provide youths the skills to become productive entrepreneurs and engender creative and innovative ideas that would enlarge the nation's economic pie and increase personal freedom. Here, TVET becomes a handy tool, as it can be both formal and informal. Such skill development of the youth empowerment must take into account: Skills to diversify the youths for self-actualization, rather than reliance on government alone, Equipping the youths to value their handwork, Training in basic literacy, numeracy and life skills should be an integral part of the whole system and The promotion of the growth and profitability of the youths for self-employment to enhance the economy. Though the neglect of vocational education is socially injurious, as it robs the nation the contribution the youths would make on national development. More importantly, the society needs competent auto mechanics, truck drivers' carpenters, plumbers, electricians, medical technicians' vocational nurses to function well for sustainable development.

Nigeria's Performance in Up-Scaling of Technical and Vocational Education Training
Skill training enhances productivity and sustains competitiveness in the global economy. Worldwide countries are renewing efforts to promote technical and vocational education and training, this is because it is the only way to prepare young people for world of work, which reaches out to the marginalized and excluded groups to engage them in income-generating livelihoods. High unemployment has been leading to increasing poverty and serious social problems in Nigeria: coincidentally there has been a decline in TVET enrolments (EFA, 2000). Less than 1percent of secondary schools is oriented towards technical and vocational skills. Therefore, there is the need to revitalize TVET as the best means to improve economic opportunities for the teaming youths of Nigeria. It is in recognition of this, that government has gone into agreement with the UNESCO's section for technical and vocational education through the National Board for Technical Education (NBTE). Currently NBTE is implementing a project that aims to better equip large numbers of young Nigerians for a world of work. A cost sharing agreement was therefore signed in 2000, between UNESCO and Nigerian Federal Ministry of Education to revise the curricula for secondary technical colleges and post-secondary polytechnics and established a new system of continuing technical staff development and training,

(EFA Reports,2000). But still the Nigerian government need to do more in view of the enormity of the problem.

Technical and Vocational Education as a Launch – Pad for Sustainable Development.

Development is a process where an economy undergoes social and economic transformation leading to a rise in the standard of living, access to basic amenities for all through knowledge.

It is in recognition of the above concept of development that TVET in empowering youth for poverty alleviation should be given utmost priority by government, having in mind the future consequence and task ahead for sustainable development. The future prospect and success of TVET would depend on the continuation and expansion of the existing training programmes, and strengthening the existing cooperation both national and international, as well as by starting non-formal training programmes for the unemployed youth and the community at large as part of government poverty alleviation efforts toward sustained welfare of the youth and development.

Poverty Alleviation Through TVET Education

The way the production forces in the economy are organized, determines the development process of any country, for most countries, the development of industry depend greatly on the private sector, with entrepreneurship playing a major role. Entrepreneurship is the capacity and attitude of a person to undertake venture, with a risk or failure. It demands that the individual be prepared to assume a reasonable degree of risk and a good leader in addition to being highly innovative. Since entrepreneurship involves leadership, leadership abilities determines a person's or organization's effectiveness, the entrepreneurship could become a major avenue to accelerate economic growth create job opportunities, many youths aspire to become successful entrepreneurs, but their ability to make use of their skills remain constrained if they are not empowered. At the policy level, TVET plays a critical access and equity role in achieving employment for youth, managing work/life balance, and providing citizenship and parental skills for youth. Therefore, expanding TVET is integral for youth in crisis or post conflict situations, tackling poverty, and promulgating cultural inclusion for tolerant peaceful society.

The youths through TVET education are encouraged to assume entrepreneurial position, as there is nothing that can surpass the effectiveness of hands on training. Through TVET the youths who are full of fresh ideas ingenuity can build up confidence and experience

early in life, so that these youths can begin to change the society into a bloomy economy thereby eradicating poverty.

TVET'S Private Sector Partnership (PPP).

TVET-private sector partnership is synonymous to, or a subset of Public-Private Sector Partnership(PPP). It is clearly distinguished from TVET-industry interaction which involves Students Industrial Work Experience, work visits, teaching practice, or internship programme. Although, TVET-industry interaction sets the momentum for engaging into Public-Private Partnership to map out strategies and initiate an integrated approach to TVET for economic development. The term TVET is seen as human and economic development strategy that inculcate practical and applied skills as well as basic scientific knowledge on students for useful living within and outside Nigeria. The private sector is that part of the economy controlled and managed by non-government organizations. The organized corporate entities like Oil companies

The Synergy Between Town and Gown in the Promotion of TVET.

TVET-private sector partnership would represent a powerful tool for pooling core capabilities, competencies and resources in achieving TVET goals on the bases of mutually agreed division of labour. It is basically seen as a contractual arrangement between TVET and private sector that would allow the private organizations to participate in the delivery of capital projects of a defined quality and quantity at agreed price for a specified period of time.

However, to have a significant impact on youth employment outcomes in an era of rapid technological change and globalization, TVET institutions will need to undergo a major transformation. They will need to: keep up to date with labour market analyses and skills forecasts to ensure that their services are forward-looking and pertinent; form closer links with the private sector and other key partners to access support for their programmes and improve the relevance of their offerings; extend their coverage to a wider pool of beneficiaries, particularly rural youth and young women, who tend to be more affected by unemployment; expand their programmes to incorporate elements known to increase the employability of youth; and upgrade their internal structures and processes to support these multiple objectives

TVET-private sector partnership can be described as a strategic cooperation in which public TVET agencies and private sector actors pool together core complimentary capabilities, competencies and resources to achieve the set goals of TVET. It is basically

referred to as a contractual agreement between TVET and private sector that allows private companies to participate in the delivery of capital projects of a defined nature and quality at an agreed price for a specified period of time. It entails the pooling and combination of resources and expertise from TVET and private sector to achieve goals that add value beyond what either sector could achieve alone. This approach is hinged on the idea that TVET and the private sectors have different potentially core complementary capabilities, competencies and resources, if properly harnessed, can help in the effective and efficient delivery of TVET.

The Importance Private Sector Partnership

The rate of the hydra-monster unemployment in the country despite TVET is 23.9%, while the level of poverty is 72% (NBS, 2011; CBN, 2011). This is also affecting many young graduates of other disciplines because unemployment is far out-weighting gainful employment opportunities. This situation tends to delimit the relevance of TVET in the competitive education and labour market, meaning that the country at large suffers economically, lacking the necessary skilled and competent manpower for employment and national development thereby creating more social problems for the country.

Today, skilled youths, even medical graduates need to know someone in order to get a job. Unemployment and underemployment situation in the country is not only disturbing but also becoming embarrassing and disgraceful. The problem of unemployment has become worsened as millions of secondary school leavers and graduates of tertiary institutions have not secured gainful employment over the years. Unemployment has posed a serious problem not only to the welfare of individuals but also to that of their families. Many able bodies and highly qualified persons who could not secure gainful employment have remained economically dependent on their parents. This is because they lack the necessary skills and competences to become self-employed and to effectively function in today's world of work. These occupational competencies and skills can only be provided through TVET. As such, the high rate of unemployment, underemployment as well as poverty among various categories of school leavers has necessitated the need for partnership between TVET and private sector. The reason for this partnership is to overcome the fiscal barriers for procuring new and modern equipment, upgrading facilities and developing staff skills, and curricula that would help to prepare and mobilize graduates for gainful employment and national development.

The Advantages of TVET-Private Sector Partnership

TVET-private sector partnership is the most effective human and economic development strategy that Nigeria needs to embrace for the mobilization of technical workforce for industrialization and national development. It is hoped that partnership between TVET and the private sector will bring on board the management practices and resources of the private sector into the TVET sector so as to improve competitiveness and increase efficiency. The understanding is that this approach will make TVET expenditure more effective and in some cases will attract financial investment from the private sector. TVET-private sector partnership can assist in the provision of more incentives that would help to source for the right-caliber of teaching and non-teaching staff and offer a wide range of modern facilities such as state-of-the-art lecture halls, laboratories, libraries, workshops, studios, and information technology services to ensure that students are provided with an environment in which they can learn both successfully and comfortably. Indeed, it is in the interest of the country that human and material as well as instructional capacity is well developed on a sustainable basis to enhance labour market productivity as well as create an enabling environment for sustainable development through learning. This resource mobilization for TVET delivery will consequently help to inculcate a solid and lasting entrepreneurship skills and employable skills on students so as to be able to secure employment after the programme; start and grow their own businesses and become self-employed and employ others. Working as self-employed or paid employed persons would help to generate high income capacities for poverty reduction and high standard of living.

YABA College of Technology, Yabatech's Collaboration with the Town in the Promotion of TVET.

This could be achieved through the following: Involve private sector partners in the design and delivery of TVET, offer on-the-job training, 'soft skills' training and career guidance, Recognize and accredit skills and experience gained outside of school, offer on-the-job training, 'soft skills' training and career guidance and Widening access: Engaging disadvantaged and marginalized groups

The TVET office will need to: Involve the private sector – including employers, parents and young people – in curriculum design and delivery to ensure the relevance and quality of TVET programmes, Offer on-the-job and soft skills training to provide young people with work experience and increase their employability, Regularly update their knowledge of the skills market to ensure that TVET offerings are up to date and relevant; Disseminate this information to students as career guidance, at an early stage and

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regularly, to help them make considered choices about their future; and Extend skills development opportunities to disadvantaged groups left behind by the education system, to increase their employability and reduce the risk of their involvement in crime and violence.

Conclusions

Unemployment among young graduates in Nigeria has become endemic and therefore requires a combination therapy. Youth unemployment can be tackled. Every young person could be given the chance that previous generations took for granted. Together we can help the young people get the jobs on which their future and those yet unborn depends. This can be achieved through entrepreneurship training in Technical Vocational Education and Training.

There is a need to establish a secure and poverty free nation for youth to become influential members of any society. Poverty, hunger, homelessness society, sickness and lack of security are paramount issues that require immediate attention of the Nigerian government, if young people are expected to become leaders of the future.

For many youths in Nigeria, these problems are daily challenges, when they cannot feed, clothe or shelter themselves or their immediate family, they surely cannot realize their full potentials, since the need for survival is so overwhelming a good number of young people have fallen victim to the pressures of survival and have ended up as arm robbers, prostitutes' scammers, or militants fighting whatever cause, give them a glimmer of hope. The failure of the government to revitalize the technical and vocational training(TVET) education with emphasis to empower the youth for self-actualization and employment to satisfy basic social needs, exacerbates these problems. It is therefore imperative to note that, the world needs educated and skilled workers with Nigerian youths at the core, and technical and vocational educational training (TVET) could fill the void.

Recommendation

These include following: Government should organized regular seminars and workshop to keep TVET teachers update on the current development in the field of TVET ,There should be massive and effective public awareness campaign to sensitize the people on the benefits of TVET in terms of employment and that TVET is not for “never-do-well” youths, There should be massive recruitment of young viable and adequate TVET

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instructors with new innovations to replace the old retiring teachers, TVET educators should be treated well with good working conditions and should be highly remunerated and motivated, Both government and private sectors should collectively provide training facilities in technical vocational institutions/centers for the acquisition of skills in TVET, Employment should not be tailored on paper and pen qualification only but also on skills acquired related to the job area, TVET-private sector partnership should be encouraged so as to provide the needed resources for the realization of the goals and objectives of TVET in Nigeria and TVET-private sector partnership should be encouraged so as to promote the development of Nigeria economic that is found to be very slow and unimpressive.

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